

Intramolecular cyclisation of photolabile thienylchromenones : synthesis of angular tetracyclic compounds

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Abstract : Photo-irradiation of 3-alkoxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4*H*-chromen-4-ones in methanol with Pyrex filtered UV-light lead to the formation of interesting angular tetracyclic compounds. In the present study, we demonstrate the formation and distribution of the photoproducts which depends upon the stability of *in situ* generated 1,4-biradicals (through type-II process).

Keywords : Photocyclisation, thienylchromenones, 1,4-biradical, substituents effect, J/Φ relationship.

Introduction

Compounds containing the chromone¹ skeleton are widely distributed in nature which exhibit multiple biological properties²⁻⁴ and interesting photoreactions⁵⁻⁷. It has been reported from our laboratory that phototransformations of chromones bearing different substituents⁸⁻¹² at positions C-2 and C-3 yield various types of interesting photoproducts through intramolecular H-abstraction. These substrates have also been used to explore the utility of H-abstraction for the organic synthesis of vinyl ethers, spiropyrans, linear and angular polycyclics.

It is evident from the above account that the photochemical study of chromones is an interesting area of research as it provides fruitful mechanistic understanding. So, we are encouraged to synthesise and study their photobehavior. In the present study, we report our investigation on the synthesis and photoreactions of 3-alkoxy-4*H*-chromen-4-ones having thiophene at C-2 position. Our main objectives related to the present work are (i) to study the effect of different substituents (at C-3) on products formation and their distribution by altering the stability of *in situ* generated 1,4-biradical and (ii) to explore more about the synthetic utility of the photo-induced intramolecular hydrogen transfer⁸⁻¹³.

Results and discussion

The photolabile substrates **3(a-d)** were synthesized by reacting the chalcones **1** with 30% H₂O₂/OH⁻ under Algar-Flynn-Oyamada reaction conditions¹⁴ and subsequent alkylation (Scheme 1) of the 3-hydroxychromenones with suitable alkylating agent in the presence of dry acetone, freshly dried K₂CO₃ and *n*-Bu₄N⁺I⁻.

The structures of these compounds **3(a-d)** were found to be consistent with their spectral parameters (IR, ¹H NMR, *vide* Experimental).

The photo-irradiation of methanolic solution of the chromenones **3(a-d)** with Pyrex filtered UV-light, under nitrogen atmosphere, produced the photoproducts **4(a-d)**. In addition to these, photolysis of chromenone **3d** also furnished the dehydrogenated photoproduct **4d'** (Scheme 2). Such photoproducts may be in small amounts, whatsoever should have also been produced from other substrates **3(a-c)**, but we were not been able to isolate them in spite of our best efforts.

It is also observed that, as the stability of the 1,4-biradicals **5** (Scheme 3), generated *in situ* through intramolecular H-abstraction, increases from **3a** (R = -H) to **3d** (R = -C₆H₅), the yield of the corresponding photoproduct also increases (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of thienylchromenones 3(a-d).

Scheme 2. Products formation upon photo-irradiation of chromenones 3(a-d).

The structure of compound **4d** was evident from its IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. A strong absorption peak at 1659 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum confirmed the presence of pyrone moiety. In the ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) spectrum, all the protons of benzenoid ring and thienyl ring appeared at expected δ values (*vide* Experimental). Five phenyl ring protons were resonated at δ 7.38–7.22. A look at the spectrum revealed that the singlet due to

two protons at δ 5.35 in **3d** (-OCH₂-) was altogether missing in **4d**. A new resonance peak at δ 4.73 (d, *J*_{4,3a} 10.2 Hz) was observed due to proton H-4.

Likewise, the structures of other cyclic dihydrophoto-products **4(a-c)** were confirmed by their spectral data.

To examine the stereochemistry of this dihydro photoproduct **4d**, the *J/Φ* relationship¹⁵ and MM2 programme¹⁶ has been invoked (Table 1). The vicinal

Table 1. Expected J/Φ relationship for the two conformations of photoproduct **4d**

Coupling protons	Conformation A ($E_{\text{kcal}} = 11.054$)		Conformation B ($E_{\text{kcal}} = 13.890$)		Observed J (Hz)
	Φ	J^a (Hz)	Φ	J^a (Hz)	
3a-4	-177.00	12.9	-50.51	5.4	10.2
3a-11b	30.12	8.61	29.84	8.65	8.7

^aExpected value.

coupling constant (3J) between H-3a and H-11b was found to be 8.7 Hz in **4d**, which reflects the *cis*-fusion of ring C and D as in accordance with the literature¹⁷. Now, regarding the stereochemical relationship of H-3a and H-4, which can be *cis* or *trans*, the use of J/Φ relationship satisfactorily indicated these to be around in *trans* relationship (Fig. 1; Conformation A). This has made the stereocentre C-4 to have *S*-configuration and stereocentre C-3a to have *R*-configuration.

Fig. 1. MM2 energy minimized structures of expected conformations of compound **4d**.

The steric energy ($E_{\text{kcal/mol}}$) calculations¹⁶ also showed that the lower energy conformation (Conformation A) is the one that explain the observed J/Φ relationship (Table 1).

The dihedral angles (Φ) and the expected J values along with steric energies are tabulated (Table 1).

The observed 3J value found in the present case for **4d** is in accordance with the J^a value calculated (Table 1) for the Conformation A, in which the protons H-3a and H-4 are in a *trans*-disposition to each other.

The structure of dehydrogenated photoproduct **4d'** was

also confirmed with the help of spectral data. On comparison of the ^1H NMR spectrums of **4d'** with that of **4d**, it was found that the resonances due to H-3a, H-11b were not aroused in former. Besides this, doublet at δ 4.73 (in **4d** due to H-4) was also absent and a new singlet due to H-4 was observed at δ 6.55. The position of H-2 and H-3 signals were found at δ 7.61 (d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.2 Hz) and δ 6.84 (d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.2 Hz) respectively.

The photo-conversions of these alkoxychromones **3(a-d)** into the angular tetracyclic compounds **4(a-d)** can be envisaged to occur through an initial H-abstraction from $-\text{OCH}_2-$ group by the excited $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of the pyrone moiety to produce 1,4-biradical **5** (Scheme 3). The ease of H-abstraction may be the result of a possible six-membered transition state in these substrates. The photoproducts **4(a-d)** has been projected to be formed through the bond formation between $\cdot\text{C}\text{H}$ - radical and the C-3' of the thiophene ring followed by the 1,5-H shift in the enol **6** (Scheme 3).

The other photoproduct **4d'** furnished from **3d** is originated directly¹⁸ from **6** (Scheme 4) in the absence of any oxidant (I_2 or O_2 etc.) by the expulsion of H_2 not via dihydro photoproduct **4d**. This was confirmed by the fact that the photoproduct **4d** on further irradiation did not undergo dehydrogenation \rightarrow yield **4d'**.

Conclusion :

The 3-alkoxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4*H*-chromen-4-ones upon photo-irradiation under nitrogen atmosphere yielded angular tetracyclic products through 1,4-biradical furnished via γ -H abstraction and distribution of these photoproducts depends upon the nature of the 3-alkoxy groups.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are thus uncorrected. The photo-irradiation was car-

Scheme 3. Mechanism of product formation through photo-irradiation.

Scheme 4. Formation of photoproduct 4d'.

ried out with a 125 W Hg lamp using a Pyrex filter. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a MB3000 FT-IR with HORIZON MB™ FTIR software from ABB Bomen using KBr pellets. Mass spectra were recorded at 3500 eV as (ESI + Q1 mode). Elemental analysis was carried on Perkin-Elmer 2400 instrument. TLC plates were coated with silica gel G (suspended in CHCl₃-MeOH) and iodine vapours were used as visualizing agent. The columns for purification were packed with silica gel (100–200 mesh) in pet. ether and left overnight before use. The yields reported are based on the amount of isolated photoproducts and are calculated by excluding the recovered starting substrates.

Synthesis of 2'-hydroxy-3-(2''-thienyl)acrylophenone (1) :

A methanolic solution (30.0 ml) of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.02 mol) was stirred with powdered NaOH (0.04 mol) and 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde (0.02 mol) at

0 °C. The reaction mixture which became deep red in colour after 30 min was further stirred for 3 h. Thereafter, it was poured on crushed ice and was neutralized with dil. HCl. The light yellow product thus obtained was filtered off, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol. Yield (79%); yellow solid; m.p. 85 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹): 1637.0 (C=O), 3084.0 (-OH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 12.77 (1H, s, -OH), 7.98 (1H, d, J_{3,2} 15.0 Hz, H-3), 7.82 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-6'), 7.43 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.7 Hz, H-5'), 7.40 (1H, d, J_{5'',4''} 5.1 Hz, H-5''), 7.37 (1H, d, J_{2,3} 15.0 Hz, H-2), 7.34 (1H, d, J_{3'',4''} 3.6 Hz, H-3''), 7.05 (1H, dd, J_{4'',5''} 5.1 Hz, J_{4'',3''} 3.6 Hz, H-4''), 6.95 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-3'), 6.88 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-4').

Synthesis of 3-hydroxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (2) :

To a methanolic solution (20.0 ml) of acrylophenone 1 (0.0007 mol), aq. NaOH solution (10.0 ml) at 0 °C was added. Then hydrogen peroxide (6.0 ml) was added to this reaction mixture dropwise over 1 h. The mixture was stirred for 4 h. The reaction was quenched by pouring the resulting mixture on crushed ice and neutralizing with dil. HCl. The solid thus obtained was filtered off, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol to obtain 2. Yield (78%); creamy white solid; m.p. 164 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹): 1600.0 (C=O), 3099.0 (-OH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃,

300 MHz) : δ 8.17 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-5), 7.96 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.63 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-6), 7.56 (1H, dd, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{5',4'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.50 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-8), 7.35 (1H, dt, J_m 1.2 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-7), 7.17 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-4').

Synthesis of 3-methoxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3a) :

3-Hydroxychromone **2** (0.01 mol), dimethylsulphate (0.01 mol), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g) and tetra-*n*-butylammoniumiodide (30.0 mg) in dry acetone (25.0 ml) were refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was removed by distillation and the reaction was quenched by pouring ice cold water to the reaction mixture. The solid was obtained by filtration that was crystallized from methanol to get pure 3-methoxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, **3a**. Yield (65%); light green solid; m.p. 76 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1633.0 (C=O), 1601.0 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.18 (1H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-5), 7.90 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.61 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.2 and 8.1 Hz, H-6), 7.56 (1H, dd, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.46 (1H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-8), 7.32 (1H, d{t}, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-7), 7.15 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.6 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-4'), 4.01 (3H, s, OCH₃) (Found : C, 65.03; H, 3.79. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀O₃S : C, 65.10; H, 3.90%).

The other ethers **3(b-d)** were synthesized by reacting 3-hydroxychromenone **2** with propargyl bromide, allyl bromide and benzyl chloride respectively by the procedure as used for compound **3a**.

3-Propargyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3b) :

Yield (74%); white solid; m.p. 115 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1639.0 (C=O), 2108.8 (C≡C), 1599.0 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.26 (1H, d, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-5), 8.06 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.71 (1H, dd, J_o 6.9 and 7.8 Hz, H-6), 7.66 (1H, d, $J_{5',4'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.57 (1H, d, J_o 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.42 (1H, dd, J_o 6.9 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.24 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-4'), 5.19 (2H, d, $J_{1',3'}$ 2.1 Hz, H-1''), 2.43 (1H, t, $J_{3'',1''}$ 2.1 Hz, H-3'') (Found : C, 67.92; H, 3.51. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀O₃S : C, 68.07; H, 3.57%).

3-Allyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3c) :

Yield (76%); green solid; m.p. 66 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1636.0 (C=O), 1604.0 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.26 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-5), 8.01 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.71 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-6), 7.63 (1H, dd, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{5',4'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.55 (1H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-8), 7.41 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, 7.8 Hz, H-7), 7.23 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 5.1 Hz, H-4'), 6.18 (1H, tdd, $J_{2'',1''}$ 6.3 Hz, $J_{2'',3''Ha}$ 10.5 Hz, $J_{2'',3''Hb}$ 17.1 Hz, H-2''), 5.45 (1H, dd, $J_{3''b,3''Ha}$ 1.5 Hz, $J_{3''Hb,2''}$ 17.1 Hz, H_b-3''), 5.28 (1H, dd, $J_{3''Ha,3''Hb}$ 1.5 Hz, $J_{3''Ha,2''}$ 10.2 Hz, H_a-3''), 4.90 (2H, m, H-1'') (Found : C, 67.21; H, 4.21. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂O₃S : C, 67.59; H, 4.25%).

3-Benzoyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3d) :

Yield (68%); brown solid; m.p. 113 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1635.0 (C=O), 1602.0 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.27 (1H, d, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-5), 7.95 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.67 (1H, t, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-6), 7.60 (1H, d, $J_{5',4'}$ 6.0 Hz, H-5'), 7.53 (1H, d, J_o 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.43–7.35 (5H, m, five protons of phenyl ring), 7.18 (1H, m, H-7), 7.10 (1H, m, H-4'), 5.35 (2H, s, -OCH₂-) (Found : C, 71.68; H, 4.17. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₄O₃S : C, 71.84; H, 4.22%).

Photoirradiation of chromenones 3(a-d) :

Photolysis of 3-methoxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3a) :

A deoxygenated methanolic solution of chromenone **3a** (1.0 mM) was irradiated in a Pyrex reactor under nitrogen atmosphere for 60 min with a 125 W Hg vapour lamp. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. The removal of solvent under reduced pressure yielded a gummy mass which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. The column was eluted with increasing proportion of benzene in benzene-pet. ether mixture yielding photoproduct **4a**.

Compound **4a** : Yield (27%); white solid; m.p. 175 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1638.0 (C=O), 1608 (C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 8.19 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-7), 7.58 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.2 and 8.1 Hz, H-8), 7.39 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-10), 7.30 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.2, 8.1 Hz, H-9), 6.30 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 6.0 Hz, H-2), 5.51 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 6.0 Hz, H-3), 4.87 (1H, d, $J_{11b,3a}$ 8.1 Hz, H-11b), 4.10 (1H, dd,

$J_{4a,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{4a,4b}$ 11.2 Hz, H-4a), 3.90 (1H, dd, $J_{4b,3a}$ 9.3 Hz, $J_{4b,4a}$ 11.2 Hz, H-4b), 3.49 (1H, ddd, $J_{3a,4a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,11b}$ 8.1 Hz, $J_{3a,4b}$ 9.3 Hz, H-3a); Mass (m/z , +Q1) : 259 (M^+ , 100) (Found : C, 65.03; H, 3.79). Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{10}O_3S$: C, 65.10; H, 3.90%).

Photolysis of 3-propargyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3b) :

A 1.0 mM methanolic solution of **3b** on photolysis for 60 min furnished **4b**.

Compound **4b** : Yield (32%); brown solid; m.p. 170 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1650.0 (C=O), 2107 (C≡C), 1602.0 (C=C); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 8.18 (1H, m, H-7), 7.51 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-8), 7.37 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-10), 7.29 (1H, dt, J_m 1.2 Hz, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-9), 6.38 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 6.0 Hz, H-2), 5.58 (1H, dd, $J_{3,3a}$ 2.7 Hz, $J_{3,2}$ 6.0 Hz, H-3), 4.90 (1H, d, $J_{11b,3a}$ 8.1 Hz, H-11b), 4.28 (1H, dd, $J_{4,2'}$ 2.1 Hz, $J_{4,3a}$ 8.4 Hz, H-4), 3.21 (1H, ddd, $J_{3a,3}$ 2.7 Hz, $J_{3a,11b}$ 8.1 Hz, $J_{3a,4}$ 8.4 Hz, H-3a), 2.59 (1H, d, $J_{2',4}$ 2.1 Hz, H-2'); Mass (m/z , +Q1) : 283 (M^+ , 100) (Found : C, 68.02; H, 3.51). Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_3S$: C, 68.07; H, 3.57%).

Photolysis of 3-allyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3c) :

A 1.0 mM methanolic solution of **3c** on photolysis for 60 min furnished **4c**.

Compound **4c** : Yield (41%); brown solid; m.p. 98 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1641.0 (C=O), 1605.0 (C=C); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 8.19 (1H, m, H-7), 7.53 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.2 Hz, H-8), 7.37 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-10), 7.29 (1H, dt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.2, 8.4 Hz, H-9), 6.33 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 6.0 Hz, H-2), 5.90 (1H, ddd, J 6.9 Hz, J_{cis} 10.5 Hz, J_{trans} 17.4 Hz, H-1'), 5.48 (1H, dd, $J_{3,3a}$ 3.0 Hz, $J_{3,2}$ 6.0 Hz, H-3), 5.39 (1H, d, J_{trans} 17.4 Hz, H-2'a), 5.32 (1H, d, J_{cis} 10.5 Hz, H-2'b), 4.91 (1H, d, $J_{11b,3a}$ 8.7 Hz, H-11b), 4.28 (1H, dd, $J_{4,1'}$ 6.9 Hz, $J_{4,3a}$ 9.3 Hz, H-4), 3.21 (1H, ddd, $J_{3a,3}$ 3.0 Hz, $J_{3a,11b}$ 8.7 Hz, $J_{3a,4}$ 9.3 Hz, H-3a); Mass (m/z , +Q1) : 285 (M^+ , 100) (Found : C, 67.41; H, 4.21). Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_3S$: C, 67.59; H, 4.25%).

Photolysis of 3-benzyloxy-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-4H-chromen-4-one (3d) :

A 1.0 mM methanolic solution of **3d** on photolysis for 60 min furnished **4d** and **4d'**.

Compound **4d** : Yield (46%); creamy solid; m.p. 161 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1659.0 (C=O), 1609.0 (C=C); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 8.20 (1H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-7), 7.56 (2H, ddd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.4, 8.7 Hz, H-8, H-9), 7.38–7.22 (6H, m, H-10 and five protons of 4-phenyl ring), 6.30 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 6.0 Hz, H-2), 5.07 (1H, dd, $J_{3,3a}$ 3.0 Hz, $J_{3,2}$ 6.0 Hz, H-3), 4.98 (1H, d, $J_{11b,3a}$ 8.7 Hz, H-11b), 4.73 (1H, d, $J_{4,3a}$ 10.2 Hz, H-4), 3.41 (1H, ddd, $J_{3a,3}$ 3.0 Hz, $J_{3a,11b}$ 8.7 Hz, $J_{3a,4}$ 10.2 Hz, H-3a); Mass (m/z , +Q1) : 335 (M^+ , 100) (Found : C, 71.64; H, 4.17). Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{14}O_3S$: C, 71.84; H, 4.22%).

Compound **4d'** : Yield (12%); yellow solid; m.p. 103 °C; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1635.0 (C=O), 1604.0 (C=C); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 8.28 (1H, dd, J_m 1.2 Hz, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-7), 7.61 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.2 Hz, H-2), 7.59 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 8.1, 8.4 Hz, H-8), 7.52 (1H, ddd, J_m 1.2 Hz, J_o 8.4 Hz, H-9), 7.38–7.22 (6H, m, H-10 and five protons of 4-phenyl ring), 6.84 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.2 Hz, H-3), 6.55 (1H, s, H-4); Mass (m/z , +Q1) : 333 (M^+ , 100) (Found : C, 72.05; H, 3.57). Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{12}O_3S$: C, 72.27; H, 3.64%).

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